

A one-dimensional vertical ecosystem model for lake dynamics¹

Fasma Diele

Istituto per le Applicazioni del Calcolo M. Picone (IAC)- CNR,
Via Amendola 122, 70100 Bari, Italy
f.diele@iac.cnr.it

Mariasilvia Giamberini

Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources (IGG) - CNR,
Via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy
mariasilvia.giamberini@igg.cnr.it

Carmela Marangi, Angela Martiradonna

Istituto per le Applicazioni del Calcolo M. Picone (IAC)- CNR,
Via Amendola 122, 70100 Bari, Italy
c.marangi@iac.cnr.it a.martiradonna@ba.iac.cnr.it

Antonello Provenzale

Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources (IGG) - CNR,
Via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy
antonello.provenzale@igg.cnr.it

Abstract

We present a modified version of an existing lake ecosystem model [6] describing a trophic chain generated by nutrients, phytoplankton and zooplankton (NPZ model). The NPZ model takes into account the vertical dynamics of the biomasses of the main species following the approach in [11]. We tailor the model to specific ecosystems by including seasonality in the dynamics of the various compartments. Moreover, different species exhibit a different behaviour with respect to diffusion and to the rate of vertical movement. With this model, we simulate the ecosystem dynamics of Alpine lakes located in study sites of the H2020 ECO-POTENTIAL project.

Keywords: Lake ecosystem dynamics, NPZ model, ADR (advection-diffusion-reaction) equation, Positive and conservative splittings.

¹This work has been carried out within the H2020 project ‘ECO-POTENTIAL: Improving Future Ecosystem Benefits Through Earth Observations’. The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 641762.

Figure 1: Protected Areas under investigation within the H2020 project ECO-POTENTIAL. 8 out of 25 protected areas include lakes.

1. Introduction

Lake ecosystems offer environmental benefits of great relevance for our quality of life. Among the ecosystem services they provide, there are not only tourism and recreation, but also the capability of mitigating the impact of floods and droughts by storing large amounts of water and releasing it during dry periods. Moreover, lakes often have a positive influence on the water quality of downstream watercourses, and contribute to the preservation of biodiversity and habitats of the surrounding area. Lakes belong to the broader category of freshwater ecosystems. Although freshwaters cover less than one per cent of the Earth's surface, they host approximately six per cent of all known animal species [13]. According to *The Red List of Threatened SpeciesTM*, 25007 species have their home in freshwaters, and more than 29% of them are currently reported as at risk of extinction [5], primarily due to a combination of anthropogenic factors like pollution, unsustainable use and exploitation of soil and water resources and introduction of alien species. Moreover, as members of the fragile family of freshwater ecosystems, lakes exhibit a strong vulnerability also with respect to climate changes [7]. Thus, it is of great importance to better understand the dynamics governing the lake ecosystem functioning in order to preserve biodiversity and ecosystem services provision in a variously threatened environment.

These are the motivations behind the present study, which is a part of the research activities carried out in ECO-POTENTIAL, a European funded project aiming at creating a unified framework for ecosystem studies and management of

Figure 2: Annual mixing at the surface and irregular mixing between the upper mixed layer and the hypolimnion of a deep lake. The lake is subject to stratification of temperature from spring to autumn in the epilimnion. On the left, the thermal profile of Lake Ohrid in the Balkan region (1998-2016) ([4]). Figure modified from <http://www.aquatic.uoguelph.ca/lakes/season/page1.htm>.

protected areas. The project analyses different ecosystem types in 25 protected areas in Europe and beyond. As can be seen in Figure 1, lakes are present in several sites under investigation within the project. The present study focuses on modeling life cycles and nutrient balance in the lakes to better understand how to preserve the proper function of the ecosystem and possibly mitigate the impact of climate change. Here we focus on modeling two aspects of the dynamics: stratification and vertical mixing. Regarding vertical mixing, we consider two types of mixing occurring at different times of the year: a) the annual mixing in the surface layer in late winter and b) the complete turnover between upper mixed layer and the hypolimnion, which takes place during cool/dry seasons when the density of the surface water gets close to the density of the bottom water. The frequency depends on several factors which change the density of the water (e.g as temperature and salinity). See Figure 2.

To take into account both the stratification in layers (epilimnion, metalimnion, hypolimnion) and the vertical mixing, as in [12], we introduce the seasonality in a one-dimensional spatial extension of the model in [6], built following the more general approach in [11].

2. A one-dimensional seasonal NPZ model

Our model includes only three compartments, describing the concentration of nutrient N (in particular phosphorous, acting as limiting agent), of phytoplankton P and zooplankton Z . All variables are measured in terms of concentrations (mass per unit volume). The concentration of N is given in phosphorus content (measured in mg-P m^{-3}), while the plankton is measured in carbon content (mg-C m^{-3}). We use the same conversion factor in the form of $P : C$ ratio q for all plankton, to convert from carbon to phosphorus. We do not explicitly describe the dynamics of bacteria as it is parametrized in the nutrient remineralization term. We make the following assumptions for two limiting factors: 1) the nutrient becomes immediately available for consumption due to its rapid transformation into soluble, bio-available phosphorus; 2) the light intensity decreases exponentially with the square of the depth x measured in meters with $0 \leq x \leq D$ and varies seasonally with respect to the time:

$$I(t, x) = I_0 + e^{-k_I^2 x^2} \frac{I_{max} - I_0}{2} \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi t}{365} \right).$$

The constants I_0 and I_{max} are normalised intensities of the Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) assumed at the surface of the lake ($x = 0$) on Dec. 31 ($t = 365$ or $t = 0$) and on midday of July 1 ($t = 182.5$) respectively, with time t in days and $t = 1$ on Jan 1st of the first year of the simulation. The constant k_I measures the reduction of light intensity with respect to the depth. By neglecting turbulence diffusion, we assume that water temperature is expressed by

$$T(t, x) = T_0 + e^{-k_T^2 x^2} \frac{T_{max} - T_0}{2} \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi(t - \delta_T)}{365} \right).$$

where δ_T is the time delay due to the fact that temperature lags light. In this way, at the surface, the temperature has an annual minimum on day δ_T .

Although visual predators may have a preference for the upper layer where light is more abundant and there is a diurnal cycle of zooplankton predation, we shall ignore these effects. Mixing associated with turbulent exchanges and sinking is modeled by diffusive and convective terms, respectively. The coefficients k_N , k_P , k_Z measure the turbulent diffusion for N , P , Z . Notice that, using diffusion to describe zooplankton vertical distribution is less justified; nevertheless this assumption is often made in literature to reproduce rather adequately both total zooplankton biomass and its spatial distribution in the water basin [11]. The turbulent diffusion coefficient k_N varies according to

$$k_N = k_N(t, x) = \mu_0 + e^{-\alpha^2 x^2} \frac{(\mu_1 - \mu_0)}{2} \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi(t - \delta_T - \delta_N)}{365} \right)$$

with δ_N delay with respect to the temperature variation; notice that the exchanges μ_0 and μ_1 with $\mu_0 > \mu_1$, are assumed at the surface ($x = 0$) on winter ($t = \delta_T + \delta_N$) and on summer ($t = 182.5 + \delta_T + \delta_N$), respectively. Turbulent

coefficients k_P and k_Z are kept constant. The process of sinking $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (W_g(T) P)$ is defined only for phytoplankton. We assume that temperature has the greatest influence on the velocity of sinking [11]. It is maximal in the epilimnion and nullifies at $T = T_0$:

$$W_g(T) = w_{gmax} \theta_s^{T-T_{max}} \frac{1 - \theta_s^{T_0-T}}{1 - \theta_s^{T_0-T_{max}}}$$

where w_{gmax} is the maximum sedimentation rate and θ_s is temperature constant of sedimentation.

2.1. Nutrient

The dynamics of nutrient concentration N (the concentration of bioavailable phosphorus) is described by

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(-k_N(t, x) \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) = -V(T)F(N, I) q P + q \rho \quad (1)$$

where $V(T)$ are the nutrient uptakes rates by phytoplankton, $F(N, I)$ the Liebig function is described later, and

$$\rho = (1 - g_p)V(T) F(N, I) P + (1 - g_z) r_z H(P) Z + (m_p P + m_z Z),$$

indicates the remineralization rate of the organic phosphorus, implicitly representing the activity of bacteria. The terms $1 - g_p$ and $1 - g_z$ indicate the fraction of resource/prey which is used for metabolism. The carbon content of P is multiplied by the molar $P : C$ ratio q to obtain the phosphorous content of phytoplankton. The term $q \rho$ in (3) represents the soluble phosphorus that is assumed to be instantaneously recycled.

2.2. Phytoplankton

The equation for phytoplankton dynamics is

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} - k_P \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} + W_g(T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = g_p V(T) F(N, I) P - m_p P - r_z H(P) Z.$$

At the right hand side of the above equation, the first term corresponds to the growth of phytoplankton by nutrient uptake which is assumed to depend not linearly on temperature according to the following relation

$$V(T) = \frac{V_p T}{\theta + T}.$$

The second term represents linear phytoplankton mortality, the third term corresponds to loss of phytoplankton due to consumption by zooplankton that obeys an Holling three-type functional form

$$H(P) = \frac{P^2}{4\epsilon_z^2 + P^2}.$$

The parameter r_z is the maximal grazing rate of zooplankton. In the Liebig function

$$F(N, I) = \min \left\{ \frac{N}{N + K_p}, \frac{I}{I + I_p} \right\},$$

the parameters K_p and I_p are half-saturation constants for nutrients and light respectively.

2.3. Zooplankton

The dynamical equation for zooplankton is

$$\frac{\partial Z}{\partial t} - k_z \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial x^2} = g_z r_z H(P) Z - m_z Z.$$

On the r.h.s. the first term is zooplankton grazing on phytoplankton and the second term describes the linear zooplankton mortality.

2.4. Boundary conditions

We set zero-flux conditions at $x = 0$ and $x = D$ for Z and P because living plankton does not enter the sediment (nor the air):

$$\begin{aligned} -k_P \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + W_g(T) P &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial Z}{\partial x} &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Boundary condition for the nutrient N at $x = 0$ are set as follows

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} = \beta N - \Phi_0.$$

Here Φ_0 represents the external nutrient input (e.g. water streams, precipitation, pollution) and βN is a loss of nutrient, proportional to N , dissolved in a fixed water volume leaving the upper layer of the lake owing, for example, to stream water removing lake water. At $x = D$

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial x}(t, L) = (N_L - N)/\tau.$$

where N_L is the nutrient reservoir in the bottom.

2.5. Parameters

The parameters used in the simulations are reported in Table 1. They refer to the Viverone Lake [12], a mesotrophic lake located in the foothills of the Italian Alps, in the north-western region Piedmont, which has been object of physical, chemical and biological monitoring characterised by the collection of abiotic (temperature, oxygen, chemical compounds) and biotic (phyto- and zooplankton) data.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Constant nutrient input at the surface	Φ_0	6.7	mg-P mt ⁻³ d ⁻¹
Nutrient loss rate at the surface (*)	β	1/30	d ⁻¹
Nutrient pool (*)	N_L	200	mg-P mt ⁻³
Nutrient relaxation time (*)	τ	30	d
Turbulent nutrient exchange (surface, winter)(*)	μ_0	1/10	mt ² d ⁻¹
Turbulent nutrient exchange (surface, summer)(*)	μ_1	1/720	mt ² d ⁻¹
Decreasing coefficient for nutrient	α	0.02	mt ⁻²
Maximum sedimentation rate	w_{gmax}	0.05	mt d ⁻¹
Temperature of sedimentation	θ_s	1.16	1/e ^{°C}
Turbulent phytoplankton diffusion	k_P	0.1	mt ² d ⁻¹
Turbulent zooplankton diffusion	k_Z	0.1	mt ² d ⁻¹
Max normalised PAR at the surface (*)	I_{max}	1	adimensional
Min normalised PAR at the surface (*)	I_0	0.3	adimensional
Decreasing coefficient for light intensity	k_I	0.02	mt ⁻²
Max temperature at the surface (*)	T_{max}	20	°C
Min temperature at the surface (*)	T_0	5	°C
Decreasing coefficient for temperature	k_T	0.02	mt ⁻²
Half-saturation for temperature (*)	θ	15	°C
Delay between light and temperature (*)	δ_T	60	d
Delay between temperature and mixing (*)	δ_N	20	d
P:C ratio (*)	q	1/100	mg-P / mg-C
Half-saturation for light (*)	I_p	0.4	adimensional
Half-saturation for phytoplankton (*)	K_p	30	mg-P mt ⁻³
Phytoplankton growth rate	V_p	8.4	d ⁻¹
Zooplankton growth rate (*)	r_z	0.2	d ⁻¹
Growth efficiency for phytoplankton (*)	g_p	0.60	adimensional
Growth efficiency for zooplankton (*)	g_z	0.70	adimensional
Half-saturation for zooplankton(*)	ϵ_z	60	mg-C mt ⁻³
Linear mortality phytoplankton (*)	m_p	1/8	d ⁻¹
Linear mortality zooplankton (*)	m_z	1/30	d ⁻¹

Table 1: Model parameters (with (*) values extracted from Table 2 in [12]).

3. Numerical simulations

A splitting and composition method is applied separating the numerical solution of the transport part (advection, diffusion) and the reaction part. Then, we approximate the elementary flows and compose the solutions. The transport step itself is subject to operator splitting. The autonomous motion of the state variables (sinking) is discretised by means of TVD (Total Variation Diminishing) advection scheme as in [10]. For the diffusion, a standard central in space scheme is used. Due to the operator split, only ordinary differential equations (ODEs) have to be treated numerically for the reaction terms. Modified Patankar schemes applied to advection-diffusion reaction problems are applied in literature [1], [2]. They are linearly implicit, unconditionally positive and mass-conservative, but they do not preserve general linear invariant. Here we use novel explicit, unconditionally positive and linear invariant conservative schemes [8].

In Figures (3)-(4)-(5) the results of our simulations along five-years time period are reported. We can appreciate how the simplified one-dimensional model is able to describe the epilimnion oscillatory dynamics induced by seasonality. The oscillations decrease with respect the depth arriving to almost nullify in the hypolimnion, this determining the lake stratification in two different layers.

4. Conclusions

We set up a simplified preliminary model to describe the trophic chain of nutrient, phytoplankton, zooplankton living in a lake. The new model is vertically one-dimensional and incorporates seasonality. The numerical approach based on a splitting and composition procedure, uses some positive schemes introduced in the recent literature [3], [8].

Despite to its simplicity, the one-dimensional NPZ model is able to provide a correct qualitative description of the different hypolimnion and epilimnion dynamics. The model is parametrized with respect the physical and biological characteristics of Viverone Lake, described in Subsection 2.5.

As a further step, we will incorporate bacterial activity and dissolved oxygen in order to study the important phenomenon of eutrophication, as well as the effect of expected temperature rise which constitute major threats affecting the trophic chain of ecosystem lake dynamics within the ECOPOTENTIAL project such as, for example, the Lake Ohrid in the Balkan region [9].

References

- [1] H. Burchard, K. Bolding, W. Kuhn, A. Meister, T. Neumann, L. Umlauf, Description of a flexible and extendable physical-biogeochemical model system for the water column, *Journal of Marine Systems* (61) **3-4** (2006), 180-211.

- [2] H. Burchard, E. Deleersnijder, A. Meister, Application of modified Patankar schemes to stiff biogeochemical models for the water column, *Ocean Dynamics* (55) **3** (2005), 326-337.
- [3] F. Diele, C. Marangi, Positive symplectic integrators for predator-prey dynamics, *Discrete & Continuous Dynamical Systems - B* (23) **7** (2018), 2661-2678.
- [4] S. Giamberini, I. Baneschi, A. Provenzale, O. Tasevska, The fate of the iconic *Salmo letnica* in Lake Ohrid under multiple threats, *Proceedings ILTER Conference*, Nantes, France, 2-4 October 2017 (<https://rza.sciencesconf.org/data/pages/Abstractsbook.pdf>)
- [5] IUCN, IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, Version 2013.2, (2013).
- [6] U. Magnea, R. Sciascia, F. Paparella, R. Tiberti, and A. Provenzale, A model for high-altitude alpine lake ecosystems and the effect of introduced fish, *Ecological modelling* **251** (2013), 211-220.
- [7] D. Markovic, S. F. Carrizo, O. Krcher, A. Walz and J. N. W. David, Vulnerability of European freshwater catchments to climate change, *Global Change Biology* (23) **9** (2017), 3567-3580.
- [8] A. Martiradonna, G. Colonna, F. Diele, Positive and mass-conservative integrators for biochemical systems, Abstract, NUMDIFF-15, 3-7 September 2018, Halle, Germany.
- [9] A. Matzinger, M. Schmid, E. Veljanoska-Sarafiloska, S. Patceva, D. Guscska, B. Wagner, B. Mller, M. Sturm, A. Wuest, Eutrophication of ancient Lake Ohrid: Global warming amplifies detrimental effects of increased nutrient inputs, *Limnology and Oceanography* **52** (2007), 338-353.
- [10] J. Pietrzak, The Use of TVD Limiters for Forward-in-Time Upstream-Biased Advection Schemes in Ocean Modeling, *Monthly Weather Review* **126** (1998), 812-830.
- [11] I. G. Prokopkin, W. M. Mooij, J. H. Janse, and A. G. Degermendzhy, A general one-dimensional vertical ecosystem model of Lake Shira (Russia, Khakasia): description, parametrization and analysis, *Aquatic ecology* (44) **3** (2010), 585-618.
- [12] A. Provenzale, J. von Hardenberg, A model ecosystem for small mesotrophic and eutrophic sub-alpine lakes, SILMAS project (Sustainable Instruments for Lake Management in the Alpine Space), technical report. Project co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the Interreg Alpine Space programme, 2009-2012.
- [13] D. L. Strayer, D. Dudgeon, Freshwater biodiversity conservation: recent progress and future challenges, *Journal of the North American Benthological Society*, **29** (2010) 344-358.

Figure 3: Nutrient dynamics

Figure 4: Phytoplankton dynamics

Figure 5: Zooplankton dynamics